

Trinity

Opening the PeV neutrino window

Anthony Brown for the Trinity collaboration

Durham University
Georgia Tech
Nagoya University
University of Utah
University of Delaware
University of Padova
University of Bari
University of Perugia
University & INFN Bari

Neutrino astrophysics

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Neutrino telescopes

- Neutrinos have:
 - Low interactional cross-sections
 - dense detector target needed
 - Low fluxes
 - large detector volumes needed

Large natural medium act as both target for interaction and calorimeter.

NOTE
 PROJECTS MARKED IN **BLUE** ARE COMPLETE OR UNDER CONSTRUCTION.
 PROJECTS MARKED IN **WHITE** ARE PROPOSED.

Trinity Detection Concept

Air-shower imaging of Earth-skimming
PeV to EeV tau neutrinos

Essentially an imaging air Cherenkov
telescope pointing at the ground

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Trinity Timeline

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Demonstrator Funding

Trinity One Funding

Trinity Observatory Funding

Demonstrator First Light

Trinity Demonstrator

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- FoV: $3.8^\circ \times 3.8^\circ$
- Camera Pixels: 256
- Angular Resolution: 0.24°
- Mirror Area: 1.36 m^2
- Sampling Speed: 100MS/s

Camera paper: [arXiv:2406.08274]

Commissioning paper: [arXiv:2503.11864]

Trinity Demonstrator

- Backgrounds
- Analysis
- Simulation Chain
- Long-term stability
- Remote Operations
- New Techniques

Camera paper: [arXiv:2406.08274]

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Commissioning

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Camera performance

- SiPM 1°C temperature stability
- Trigger rate of ~1 Hz
- UV flasher with ns timing
- No dead pixels
- 5% flatfielding stability

Optics performance

- Point spread function contained within one camera pixel.

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Optics performance: alignment

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Optics performance: alignment

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U.S. DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION FEDERAL AVIATION ADMINISTRATION CERTIFICATE OF WAIVER	
ISSUED TO	Adam Otte Responsible Party: Adam Otte Waiver Number: 107W-2024-00186
ADDRESS	3591 Sunderland Cir NE Brookhaven, GA 30319
This certificate is issued for the operations specifically described hereinafter. No person shall conduct any operation pursuant to the authority of this certificate, except in accordance with the standard and special provisions contained in this certificate, and such other requirements of the Federal Aviation Regulations not specifically waived by this certificate.	
OPERATIONS AUTHORIZED Small Unmanned Aircraft System (sUAS) operations at night and during civil twilight without anti-collision lights meeting the requirements of § 107.29(a)(2) & (b); Small Unmanned Aircraft System (sUAS) operations beyond the visual line of sight of the remote pilot in command (PIC); sUAS operations higher than 400 feet above ground level (AGL), when not within a 400 foot radius of a structure.	
LIST OF WAIVED REGULATIONS BY SECTION AND TITLE 14 CFR §§ 107.29(a)(2) & (b)—Anti-collision light requirement for operations at night and during periods of civil twilight. 107.31—Visual line of sight aircraft operation, 107.33(b) & (c)(2)—Visual observer and 107.51(b)—Operating limitations for small unmanned aircraft (sUA) - Altitude.	
STANDARD PROVISIONS	
1. A copy of the application, made for this certificate, shall be attached to and become a part hereof. 2. This certificate shall be presented for inspection upon the request of any authorized representative of the Administrator of the Federal Aviation Administration or of any State or municipal official charged with the duty of enforcing local laws or regulations. 3. The holder of this certificate shall be responsible for the strict observance of the terms and provisions contained herein. 4. This certificate is nontransferable.	
NOTE—This certificate constitutes a waiver of those Federal rules or regulations specifically referred to above. It does not constitute a waiver of any State law or local ordinance.	
SPECIAL PROVISIONS	
Special Provisions 1 to 34, inclusive, are set forth on the attached pages.	
This Certificate of Waiver is effective from June 1, 2024, to January 1, 2026, and is subject to cancellation at any time upon notice by the Administrator or an authorized representative.	
BY DIRECTION OF THE ADMINISTRATOR ADAM A VETTER Adam Vetter Tactical Operations Manager FAA Western Service Center Digitally signed by ADAM A VETTER Date: 2024.05.29 13:13:33 -0700	

Data Set

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Data collection period	Oct 2024 to June 2025
Total time span	346 hours
# triggered events	1 million

■ Best ■ Partially Good ■ Weather ■ Moon ■ Other

Sofia Stepanoff @ Georgia Tech

Event Selection

Image Pixels:
Pixels in the
cleaned
image

Size:
Sum signal of all
pixels in the
cleaned image

497 events
0.7 hours/event

Data Set

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Demonstrator

- (No) Backgrounds ✓
- Analysis ✓
- Simulation chain ✓
- Long-term operational stability ✓
- Remote operations ✓
- New techniques ✓

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Trinity Timeline

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Outlook: Trinity One

- First telescope of Trinity Observatory
- Rotates in azimuth
- FoV $5^\circ \times 60^\circ$
- 40 m^2 mirror area
- 0.15° optical PSF
- 13,200 pixel camera

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Trinity One Effective Area

Neutrinos from a TXS 0506+056-like Source

Petropoulou et al. 2020

David Raudales Oseguera @ Georgia Tech

Heavy Dark Matter

Take home points

- The Trinity concept shows excellent promise, bridging the energy gap between what IceCube sees and the event KM3NET saw
- The first phase of Trinity is complete
 - Trinity is background free
- We are ready for Trinity One
 - Will detect astrophysical neutrinos in 5 years
 - Trinity's excellent point source sensitivity leads to the potential discover of the first PeV neutrino point source